

The effect of Thermophoresis and Brownian motion in heat and mass transport of magneto hydrodynamics stagnation point flow in a micro polar fluid over an exponential vertical Sheet

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Abstract. This paper examines stagnation point flow of MHD micro polar fluid with heat and mass movement in an exponentially stretching /shrinking vertical sheet with effect thermophoresis and Brownian progress. A set of similarity variables is operating to transfer the system of partial differential equation (PDE's) to ordinary differential equation (ODEs). The ordinary differentials equation is solved numerically in Mat lab using BVP4c. The variation of various parameters is found with respect to velocity, angular velocity, concentration and temperature profiles. The results are plotted graphically with more accuracy and conclusion are given for all paper.

INTRODUCTION

Heat and mass transfer is the rate of heat transfer through the medium such as by convection, conduction and radiation. When the heat is transferred as vibration from one molecule to another will bring lot of changes in the flow of fluids. The main application of heat transport is the fins in AC and refrigeration as well as the turbine system. The main application of mass transfer is absorption evaporation, drying, precipitation membrane filtration and distillation. Micro polar fluids are complex fluids with microstructures and few examples are animal blood and liquid crystals, Ferro fluids bubbly liquids etc. since it accommodates intrinsic polarities. The micro polar fluids are fluids which contains a remission of small body fluid elements like large dumbbell molecules. The dust particles or fog contains in a gas may also being a model for micro polar fluid dynamics.

The first proposal of simple fluids was done by Eringen.et.al [1](#). It is very complicated to solve since very large equation are included in it. So he reworked and gave with short equation in micro polar fluids [2](#). The flow past a stretching sheet was first introduced by crane.et.al [3](#) & [4](#). Later the boundary layer theory for micro polar fluids was studied by peddison.et.al [5](#). Equivalent solution of the flow analysis in a boundary layer of micro polar fluid which is incompressible over a semi-infinite plate was investigated by Ahmedi.et.al [6](#). Later on the Gorla.et.al [7](#) studied heat transfer in micro polar fluid and its boundary layer flow analysis moved in a flat plate.

In three dimensional flow analysis both heat and mass transportation processes was done towards a steady stretching surface was studied by Lakmisha.et.al [8](#). Again with a small modification in application of micropolar fluids theory was discussed by Lukaszeuicz.et.al [9](#). Aziz.et.al [10](#) studied the transmission of thermal and mass transport processes of an unsteady fluid moved in a stretching sheet in occurrence of chemical reaction. Micropolar fluid flow survey to the stagnation point which is moved to a stretching sheet was examined by Nazar.et.al [11](#).

Shu.et.al [12](#) investigated fundamental solution for micropolar fluids. Attia.et.al [13](#) studied, in the heat exchange procession to a stagnation point flow of a micropolar fluid in presence of uniform suction or blowing. The micropolar fluid with viscous dissipation and mixed convection over an exponentially stretching sheet was discussed by abd-el-aziz [14](#). Ishak.et.al [15](#) investigated the micropolar fluid flow and stagnation point flow in a shrinking sheet.

A pair of force in an unsteady three dimensional fluid passes over a stretched surface in presence of chemical reaction was investigated by hayat.et.al [16](#). A mixed convection of magneto hydrodynamics, Unsteady flow both heat and mass transport over a vertical plane was studied by Aurangzib.et.al [17](#). In MHD three dimensional micropolar fluid theory, the Numerical simulation of fluid motion near stagnation point was investigated by Borrelli.et.al [18](#). Dash.et.al [19](#) was discussed numerical way to Boundary layer stagnation point flow past in a stretching/ shrinking sheet. Soid.et.al [20](#) investigated MHD stagnation point flow over a stretching/shrinking sheet in a micropolar fluid with a slip boundary. Mishra.et.al [21](#) examined micropolar fluid flow with naturally convective processes which is moved towards a dwindle sheet in existence of thermal source. Rehman.et.al [22](#) studied in thermophysical variation for three dimensional Nano-material flow movement near the stagnation point in presence of magneto hydrodynamics in an exponential stretching sheet.

Lund.et.al [23](#) discussed the triple solution convective variation in magneto hydrodynamics (MHD) stagnation point flow of casson fluid past through a vertical exponential stretching/shrinking surface. Waini.et.al [24](#) discussed hybrid Nano fluid flow past through a stagnation point of an exponentially stretching/shrinking vertical sheet in presence of buoyancy effects. Lakshmidevi.et.al [25](#) studied the MHD Nano fluid moved in a vertical plane with the chemical reaction processes, radiation effect and activation energy. This fluid has tendency to float. Song.et.al [26](#) examined Nonlinear thermally radiation heat transit for Brinkman type micro polar Nano-material over an included plane with transferable Microorganisms moved in an exponential heat source. The present article discussed the heat and mass transport process of micropolar fluid in an exponential stretching/ shrinking vertical sheet.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Consider the vertical flow of micropolar fluid to a stagnation point with thermophoresis and Brownian motion. The x axis is assigned vertically to the surface and y axes is orthogonal to it with the origin 0. From the basic analysis the free stream velocity $u_e(x)=ae^{x/L}$ where $a>0$ (constant) and L is reference length and the exponential velocity $u_w(x)=be^{x/L}$ when the surface is stretched ($b>0$) shruck($b<0$) or $b=0$ is for the static surface. The surface temperature is given as $T_w(x)=T_\infty+T_0e^{2x/L}$ and its concentration is $C_w(x)=C_\infty+C_0e^{2x/L}$ where T_0 , C_0 is a constant and T_∞ and C_∞ are ambient temperature and concentration. The governing equations are

Continuity Equation:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

Momentum Equation:

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = u_e \frac{\partial u_e}{\partial x} + \left(v + \frac{k}{\rho}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{k}{\rho} \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} + g\beta_T(T - T_\infty) - \frac{\sigma B^2}{\rho}(u - u_e) + g\beta_c(C - C_\infty) = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Angular Momentum Equation:

$$u \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} = \left(\frac{\chi}{\rho j}\right) \frac{\partial^2 N}{\partial y^2} + \frac{k}{\rho j} \left(2N + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right) \quad (1.3)$$

Temperature Equation:

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \left(\frac{k}{\rho c_p} \right) \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} + \tau \left[D_B \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1.4)$$

Concentration equation:

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D_B \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k_r (c - c_\infty) \quad (1.5)$$

The boundary condition required for the flow are

$$u = u_w, v = 0, T = T_w, N = -m \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}, C = C_w, \text{ at } y = 0$$

$$u \rightarrow u_e, T \rightarrow T_\infty, C \rightarrow C_\infty, N \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty \quad (1.6)$$

Whereas, u & v denotes the component of velocity along x & y direction respectively. The symbol ν is kinematic viscosity, μ is well known as the dynamic viscosity, ρ is the density of fluid, N is the micro rotation of fluid, j is the micro inertia per unit mass, γ is the spin gradient viscosity is the vortex viscosity, T is the temperature of fluid, L is the reference length, K^* is the thermal conductivity of the fluid, c_p is the specific heat, T_0 being a constant which measures the rate of temperature increment along the sheet and T_∞ is the free stream temperature assumed to be constant. It is well known that $n=0$ is known as strong concentrate particle which flows close to the micro elements to the wall surface that unable to rotate. For $n=0.5$ the anti-symmetric part of the stress tensor vanishes and denote weak concentrations whereas $n=1$ is used for modeling of turbulent boundary layer flows.

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{a}{2\nu L}} e^{\frac{x}{2L}} \quad u = a e^{\frac{x}{L}} f'(\eta) \quad v = -\sqrt{\frac{av}{2L}} e^{\frac{x}{2L}} (f(\eta) + \eta f'(\eta))$$

$$\theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T - T_w} \quad \phi(\eta) = \frac{C - C_\infty}{C - C_w} \quad N = a \sqrt{\frac{a}{2\nu L}} e^{\frac{3x}{2L}} h(\eta) \quad (1.7)$$

Where η is similarity variable, where u and v denote the stream function that the continuity equation is satisfied. Thus the transformed ordinary differential equations are

$$(1 + K) f''' + f f'' - 2 f'^2 - M (f' - 1) + K h' + 2 \lambda \theta + 2 \delta \phi + 2 = 0 \quad (1.8)$$

$$\left(1 + \frac{K}{2}\right)h'' - K(2h + f') - 3f'h + fh' = 0 \quad (1.9)$$

$$p_r(4f'\theta - f\theta') - \left(1 + \frac{4R}{3}\right)\theta'' - N_b\theta'\varphi' - N_T\theta^2 = 0 \quad (1.10)$$

$$-Le p_r(4f'\varphi - f\varphi') + \varphi'' + \frac{N_T}{N_B}\theta'' + Le p_r\gamma\varphi = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

With the boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} f(\eta) = 0, f'(\eta) = \varepsilon, \theta(\eta) = 1, h(\eta) = -mf''(\eta), \varphi(\eta) = 1, as\eta = 0 \\ f'(\eta) = 1, \theta(\eta) \rightarrow 0, h(\eta) \rightarrow 0, f''(\eta), \varphi(\eta) \rightarrow 0, as\eta = \infty \end{aligned} \quad (1.12)$$

Where

$K = \frac{k}{\mu}$ is the material parameter, $M = \frac{2\sigma B_0^2 L}{\rho a}$ is magnetic parameter, $\lambda = \frac{g\beta_T T_0 2L}{a^2}$ & $\gamma = \frac{g\beta_c c_0 2L}{a^2}$ buoyancy parameter, $Le = \frac{\alpha}{D_B}$ is Lewis number, $Pr = \frac{\gamma}{\alpha}$ is prandtl number, $N_b = \frac{D_B \rho c_p (c_w - c_\infty)}{p c_f \gamma}$ Brownian motion, $N_T = \frac{D_T \rho c_p (T_w - T_\infty)}{T_\infty p c_f \gamma}$ is thermophoresis parameter and $R = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{K^*}$ is radiation parameter.

NUMERICAL SOLUTION

The governing equation of this problem has been transformed into the set of coupled nonlinear boundary layer equations with the boundary conditions and then it is solved by using Bvp4c method. To study the flow characteristics, the behavior of various non dimensional parameters which is involved in this problem on the dimensionless velocity, angular velocity, temperature and concentration are studied numerically with the help of graph.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Numerical computations were done to get the insight of physical problem for MHD boundary layer micro polar fluid flow through exponentially stretching sheet. The impact of various flow controlling parameters like magnetic parameter(M), micro polar parameter(K), chemical reaction parameter (γ), prandtl number (Pr), Lewis number (le), Brownian Parameter(Nb), thermophoresis parameter (Nt), Buoyancy parameter(δ) and (λ) on velocity, micro rotation, temperature and concentration profile with the graphical representation.

Figure: 1, Figure:2, Figure 3, Figure 4 represents the influence of magnetic parameter with respect to velocity, angular velocity, temperature and concentration profile. The increases in magnetic parameter(M) increases the concentration and temperature profile whereas velocity and angular velocity profile decreases.

Fig 1: Influence of Magnetic Parameter(M) in velocity Profile with $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$.

Fig 2: Influence of Magnetic Parameter(M) in velocity Profile with $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Fig 3: Influence of Magnetic Parameter(M) in Temperature Profile with $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Fig 4: Influence of Magnetic Parameter(M) in Concentration Profile with $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8 depicts the variation of micro polar parameter(K) on velocity, angular velocity, temperature and concentration profile. When Micro polar parameter (K) increases the velocity and angular velocity, temperature profile increases whereas concentration decreases.

Fig 5: Influence of Micropolar Parameter(K) in velocity Profile with $M=2=R$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Fig 6: Influence of Micropolar Parameter(K) in Angular Velocity Profile with $M=2=R$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Fig 7: Influence of Micropolar Parameter(K) in Temperature Profile with $M=2=R$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Fig 8: Influence of Micropolar Parameter(K) in Concentration Profile with $M=2=R$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$

Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11, Figure 12 illustrate the influence of Radiation parameter(R) on velocity, angular velocity, temperature and concentration profile. When radiation parameter(R) increases the temperature and velocity profile and concentration profile decreases. In angular velocity when the radiation parameter (R) increases the angular velocity decreases initially and after certain point there is increases profile.

Fig 9: Influence of Radiation Parameter(R) in velocity Profile with $M=2$ $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$, $K=1$

Fig 10: Influence of Radiation Parameter(R) in Angular Velocity Profile with $M=2$ $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1$, $K=1$

Fig 11: Influence of Radiation Parameter(R) in Temperature Profile with $M=2$ $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1, K=1$

Fig 12: Influence of Radiation Parameter(R) in Concentration Profile with $M=2$ $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=\delta=2$, $\gamma=1, K=1$

Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15, Figure 16 Shows that the influence of Buoyancy parameter(δ) on velocity, angular velocity, temperature and concentration profile. When the Buoyancy parameter(δ) increases the velocity also increases whereas the temperature and concentration decreases. Regarding angular velocity, the graphical representation shows initially the angular velocity decreases and after certain point it slightly increases.

Fig 13: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(δ) in velocity Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=M=R=2$, $\gamma=1$, $K=1$

Fig 14: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(δ) in Angular velocity Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\lambda=M=R=2$, $\gamma=1$, $K=1$

Fig 15: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(δ) in Temperature Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, Nb=0.7, Nt=0.2, \lambda=M=R=2, \gamma=1, K=1$

Fig 16: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(δ) in Concentration Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, Nb=0.7, Nt=0.2, \lambda=M=R=2, \gamma=1, K=1$

Figure17, Figure 18, Figure 19, Figure 20 interpret the influence of Buoyancy Parameter(λ) in velocity, temperature and concentration profile. When Buoyancy parameter (λ) increases there is decreasing in temperature and concentration profile whereas the velocity and angular velocity profile increases.

Fig 17: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(λ) in Velocity Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\delta=M=R=2$, $\gamma=1$, $K=1$

Fig 18: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(λ) in Angular Velocity Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\delta=M=R=2$, $\gamma=1$, $K=1$

Fig 19: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(λ) in velocity Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, Nb=0.7, Nt=0.2, \delta=M=R=2, \gamma=1, K=1$

Fig 20: Influence of Buoyancy Parameter(λ) in velocity Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, Nb=0.7, Nt=0.2, \delta=M=R=2, \gamma=1, K=1$

Figure 21 details about the variation of chemical reaction parameter (γ) on concentration profile. When chemical Reaction parameter (γ) increases the concentration also increases.

Fig 21: Influence of Chemical Reaction Parameter(γ) in velocity Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nb=0.7$, $Nt=0.2$, $\delta=\lambda=M=R=2$

Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24 characterize the influence of Brownian Motion (Nb) on velocity, temperature and angular velocity profile. When Brownian motion (Nb) increases the velocity and temperature profile increases, whereas in angular velocity, initially for some point there is decrement in graph and after certain point there is an increment.

Fig 22: Influence of Brownian Motion(Nb) in velocity Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, pr=0.72, Nt=0.2, \delta=\lambda=M=R=2$

Fig 23: Influence of Brownian Motion(Nb) in Angular Velocity Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, pr=0.72, Nt=0.2, \delta=\lambda=M=R=2$

Fig 24: Influence of Brownian Motion(Nb) in Temperature Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $pr=0.72$, $Nt=0.2$, $\delta=\lambda=M=R=2$.

Figure 25 and Figure 26 outlines the influence of Prandle Number (Pr) on concentration and temperature profile. When Prandle number(Pr) increases the temperature and concentration decreases.

Fig 25: Influence of Prandle Number (Pr) in Temperature Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nt=0.2$, $\delta=\lambda=M=R=2$, $Nb=0.7$

Fig 26: Influence of Prandle Number (Pr) in Concentration Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $Nt=0.2$, $\delta=\lambda=M=R=2$, $Nb=0.7$.

Figure 27 and Figure 28 illustrates that the influence of Thermophoresis Parameter(N_t) on concentration and temperature profile. When Thermophoresis Parameter(N_t) increases the concentration and temperature profile also increases.

Fig 27: Influence of Thermophoresis Parameter(N_t) in Temperature Profile with $K=1, \epsilon=0.5, m=0.5, Le=1, \delta=\lambda=M=R=2, Nb=0.7, \gamma=1$

Fig 28: Influence of Thermophoresis Parameter(Nt) in Concentration Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $Le=1$, $\delta=\lambda=M=R=2$, $Nb=0.7$, $\gamma=1$

Fig 29 demonstrates the influence of Lewis Number(Le) on concentration profile. When Lewis Number(Le) increases the concentration profile decreases.

Fig 29: Influence of Lewis Number (Le) in Concentration Profile with $K=1$, $\epsilon=0.5$, $m=0.5$, $\delta=\lambda=M=R=2$, $Nb=0.7$, $\gamma=1$, $Nt=0.2$

CONCLUSION

When Magnetic Parameter(M) increases velocity and angular velocity decreases and temperature and concentration increases. If Micropolar parameter(K) increases the velocity and angular velocity increases and the temperature and concentration profile decreases. When radiation parameter(R) increases the temperature and velocity also increases and concentration decreases. When Buoyancy parameter (δ, λ) increases the velocity increases and temperature concentration decreases. When Brownian Motion (Nb) increases the velocity and concentration also increases. When Prandtl Number(Pr) increases the temperature and concentration decreases. When chemical reaction(γ) and thermophoresis parameter(Nt) increases the concentration also increases whereas for Lewis Number(Le) the concentration profile decreases.

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